

A CRITICAL REVIEW ON ANTIPYRETIC (JWARAHARA) DRUGS OF GUDUCHYADIVARGA, FROM BHAVAPRAKASA NIGHANTU WSR TO FEBRILE CONDITIONS

Dr. AVK Lakshmi Prasanna D.¹, Dr. K. Madhusudana Rao², Dr. Yamini Diwakar³,
Dr. T. Leela Rani⁴

Post Graduate Scholar¹, Professor & HOD², Assistant Professor^{3,4}

Dept. of PG studies in Dravyaguna, Dr.NRS Government Ayurvedic College,
Vijayawada Andhra Pradesh.

Article Received on 28 Nov. 2025,
Article Revised on 18 Dec. 2025,
Article Published on 01 Jan. 2026,
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18095693>

*Corresponding Author

Dr. AVK Lakshmi Prasanna D.

Post Graduate Scholar, Dept. of PG
Studies in Dravyaguna, Dr.NRS
Government Ayurvedic College,
Vijayawada Andhra Pradesh.

How to cite this Article: Dr. AVK Lakshmi Prasanna D., Dr. K. Madhusudana Rao, Dr. Yamini Diwakar, Dr. T. Leela Rani. (2026). A Critical Review on Antipyretic (Jwarahara) Drugs Of Guduchyadivarga, From Bhavaprakasa Nighantu Wsr To Febrile Conditions. World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences, 15(1), 207–215.

This work is licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

ABSTRACT

The *Jwarahara Dravyas* of the *Guduchyadivarga*, occupy a central role in Ayurvedic chikitsa in the management of *Jwara* (fever), which is considered one of the most critical disease conditions described in classical texts. These herbs, including *Guduchi*, *Nimba*, *Vasa*, *Parpataka*, and *Sindhuvara* etc., exhibit *Tikta Rasa*, making them particularly effective in pacifying *Pitta* dosha, which are commonly aggravated in *Jwara* (fever). Clinically, they are relevant in viral fevers, malaria, dengue, typhoid, even covid-19 and post-febrile debility. *Guduchi* proved to be a boon during covid pandemic. Their broad-spectrum anti-inflammatory, immunomodulatory, hepatoprotective, and antipyretic properties bridge the ancient Ayurvedic understanding with modern biomedical relevance. Thus, the *Guduchyadivarga*, provides a holistic and foundational pharmacological group for fever management in both acute and chronic contexts, aligning with the Ayurvedic principle of treating the root cause rather than just the symptom.

KEYWORDS: *Bhavaprakasha Nighantu*, *Guduchyadivarga*, *Jwara*.

INTRODUCTION

The *Bhavaprakasha Nighantu* details a wide range of medicinal drugs, expanding the Ayurvedic Materia Medica considerably, authored by *Bhavamishra* in the 16th century covering plant-based, mineral, and animal-derived drugs, as well as dietary articles. *Bhavamishra's* approach integrates traditional formulations with newly introduced drugs of that period. It goes beyond simple listings, providing information on regional names, properties, actions, and therapeutic uses of each of the substances. It categorizes medicinal drugs into 23 *Vargas* (groups), covering plant-based, mineral, and animal-derived drugs, as well as dietary articles based on similarities in their morphology, properties, pharmacological actions, etc., This systematic classification aids in understanding and utilizing these substances effectively for management of diseases and preservation of health. In *Ayurveda*, *Jwara* is defined as the manifestation of *Tridosha* predominantly pitta. Cakrapani.^[1] opines *jwara pittasya pradhanatwaat agneyabhidaanam*) which means pitta is the dominant dosha in all *jwara* along with *Ama* affecting both *Sharira and Manas*. According to various Acharyas, *Jwara* originated from anger of *Lord Shiva* and it takes away the life of living beings. According to Charaka *Samhita*, it is the first and most important among all diseases (*Roganam Shiraso Jwara*). The special manifestations of *jwara are: Santapa* (temperature), *Aruchi* (anorexia), *Trushna* (excessive thirst), *Angamarda* (malaise, body aches with heaviness), *Hrudi Vyatha*. Acharya *Susruta* has mentioned *Jwara* as King of diseases. From a modern standpoint, fever is a regulated rise in body temperature, often as a response to infection, inflammation, or autoimmune activity. *Guduchyadivarga*, as classified in *Bhavaprakasha Nighantu*, enlists *Jwarahara Dravyas* or drugs that pacify *Jwara* (fever). *Guduchyadivarga*, primarily emphasizes *Tikta - Rasa* herbs that act through *Dipana*, *Amapachana*, and *Srotoshodhana* effects (Purification) and balancing *Pitta dosha*. Specific doshaja *jwara* drugs has also been specially mentioned in this *varga* like *Sindhuvara* for *Kaphaja jwara*, *Gunja* for *Vatapitta jwara*.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Material related to *Jwaragana Dravya's* is collected from *Guduchyadivarga*, of *Bhavaprakasha Nighantu*.^[2] Classical Ayurvedic literatures, textbooks and from various scientific published journals. The available commentaries of the Ayurvedic Samhitas Previous Research Papers, Various National or International journals were also referred to collect relevant matter.

Review of Literature

Table 1: List of *Jwaraghna Dravyas of Guduchyadi Varga*.

S. No	Drug	Botanical Name	Rasa	Guna	Virya	Vipaka	Doshakarma
1	Guduchi	<i>Tinospora cordifolia</i>	Katu, Tikta, Kashaya	Laghu	Ushna	Madhura	Tridoshahara
2	Bilwa	<i>Aegle marmelos</i>	Katu, Tikta, Kashaya	Snigdha	Ushna	-	Vatakaphahara
3	Gambhari	<i>Gmelina arborea</i>	Madhura, Kashaya, Tikta	Guru	Ushna	-	-
4	Paatala	<i>Stereospermum suaveolens</i>	Kashaya, Tikta	-	Ushna	-	Tridoshahara
5	Agnimantha	<i>Clerodendron phlomidis</i>	Katu, Tikta, Kashaya, Madhura	-	Ushna	-	Kaphavatahara
6	Syonaka	<i>Oroxylum indicum</i>	Kashaya ,	-	Sita	Katu	-
7	Shaalaparni	<i>Desmodium gangeticum</i>	Tikta, Madhura	-	-	-	Tridoshahara
8	Prishniparni	<i>Uraria picta</i>	Madhura rasa	-	Ushna	-	Tridoshahara
9	Brihati	<i>Solanum indicum</i>	Katu, Tikta	-	Ushna	-	-
10	Kantakari	<i>Solanum xanthocarpum</i>	Tikta ,Katu	Ruksha, Sara	-	Katu	-
11	Gokshura	<i>Tribulus terrestris</i>	Madhura	-	Sita	-	-
12	Jivanti	<i>Leptadenia reticulata</i>	Madhura	Snigdha	Sita	-	Tridoshahara
13	Mudgaparni	<i>Phaseolus trilobus</i>	Tikta, Madhura	-	-	-	-
14	Mashaparni	<i>Teramnus labialis</i>	Tikta, Madhura	Ruksha	Sita	-	Vatapittahara
15	Eranda	<i>Ricinus communis</i>	Madhura	Guru	Ushna	-	-
16	Sehunda	<i>Euphorbia nereifolia</i>	Katu	Laghu, Tikshna	Ushna	-	-
17	Dattura	<i>Datura metel</i>	Kashaya, Madhura, Tikta	Guru	Ushna	-	-
18	Aatarusha (Vasa)	<i>Adhatoda vasica</i>	Tikta, Kashaya	Laghu	Sita	-	Kaphapittahara
19	Parpataka	<i>Fumaria parviflora</i>	Tikta	-	Sita	-	-
20	Katrina	<i>Cymbopogon martiniic</i>	Kashaya, Tikta	-	-	Katu	-
21	Gandadurva	<i>Cynodon dactylon</i> (variety)	Tikta, Kashaya, Madhura	-	-	Katu	Kaphapittahara
22	Patha	<i>Cissampelos pariera</i>	Katu	Tikshna	Ushna	-	Vatasleshmahara
23	Swetatrivrit	<i>Ipomea turpethum</i>	-	-	Ushna	-	Vatahara
24	Sarapunkha	<i>Tephrosia purpurea</i>	Tikta, Kashaya	Laghu	-	-	-
25	Yavasa	<i>Alhagi pseudalhaghi</i>	Madhura, Tikta, Kashaya	Laghu	Sita	-	Kaphahara
26	Kumari	<i>Aloe barbadensis</i>	Tikta, Madhura	-	Sita	-	-
27	Trayamana	<i>Gentiana kurroo</i>	Kashaya, Tikta	-	-	-	Pittakaphahara
28	Murva	<i>Marsdenia tenacissima</i>	Madhura, Tikta	Guru	-	-	Tridoshahara
29	Kakamachi	<i>Solanum nigrum</i>	-	-	Ushna	-	Tridoshahara
30	Brahmi	<i>Bacopa monnieri</i>	Tikta, Kashaya, Madhura	Laghu, Sara	Sita	Madhura	-
31	Mandukaparni	<i>Centella asiatica</i>	Tikta, Kashaya, Madhura	Laghu, Sara	Sita	Madhura	-
32	Suvarchala	<i>Cleome gynandra</i>	Ruksha, Sara, Guru	-	Sita	Madhura	-

33.	Devadali	<i>Luffa echinata</i>	Tikta	-	-	-	Kaphahara
34.	Gojihwa	<i>Launaea asplenifolia</i>	-	-	Sita	-	Kaphapittahara
35.	Kukundara	<i>Blumea lacera</i>	Katu, Tikta	-	-	-	-
36.	Sariva	<i>Hemidesms indicus</i>	Madhura	Snigdha, Guru	-	-	Tridosahara
37.	Nimba	<i>Azadirachta indica</i>	Tikta, kashaya	Laghu	Sita	Katu	Kaphapittahara
38.	Sindhuvara	<i>Vitex negundo</i>	Tikta, Kashaya, Katu	Laghu	-	-	Kapha jwara
39.	Gunja	<i>Abrus precatorius</i>	-	-	-	-	Vatapitta jwara

Etiopathogenesis of Jwara in Ayurveda

Jwara.^[2] is caused by the accumulation of vitiated dosa at the site of digestion which further afflicts the digestion and thermal regulation in the body. Considering the basic tools for comprehensive understanding of disease, the vitiated *vayu*, when gets into the *amashaya* (stomach), afflicts *agni* and vitiates the first *dhatu (rasa)* created through this vitiated digestion process. This (vitiating admixture of *vayu* and *rasa* blocks the channels associated with *rasa* and *sweda (rasa and swedavaha srotas)*, adversely affecting the digestive processes and moving that heat (*Pachaka pitta*) out of its locus into other parts of the body. This excess heat leads to Jwara.

Etiopathogenesis of Jwara based on Ayurveda and Modern Pathologies

Most pharmacological studies of various fevers and efficacy of herbal drugs from *Guduchyadivarga*, can be broadly classified into 4 pathologies which can also be correlated to ayurvedic terminologies were enumerated here in this study. Various references stating the efficacy of drugs from contemporary sciences research were enumerated for establishing their efficacy.

Table 2: Correlation of Ayurvedic and Modern Causes of Fever.

Ayurvedic Concept	Modern Correlate
<i>Ama Dushti</i>	Endotoxemia
<i>Agnimandya</i>	Impaired digestion / gut immunity
<i>Pitta-Rakta Dushti</i>	Inflammation / Infection
<i>Krimi</i>	Bacterial/parasitic infection

Pharmacological Actions (Karma) of Jwaraghna Dravya

All the dravya used in management of fever should have the following actions to pacify jwara and restore health. Drugs either single or as a gana (group) or in combinations have either one, two or multiple actions which are useful in the management of jwara.

Table 3: Correlation of Action of *Jwaraghna Dravya*.

Karma	Mode of Action
<i>Jwaraghna</i>	Reduces fever via Tridosha shamana, especially Pitta and Rakta dosha
<i>Agni Dipana</i>	Enhances Agni to reduce Ama - a key cause of Jwara
<i>Ama Pachana</i>	Helps digest undigested material (Ama Pachana)/toxin removal
<i>Raktashodhaka/Raktaprasadana</i>	Many of these are blood purifiers, addressing Pitta-Rakta vitiated fevers
<i>Rasayana</i>	Especially Guduchi - boosts immunity and dhatu integrity
<i>Vishaghna</i>	Antitoxic action helpful in fevers of viral or unknown origin
<i>Krimighna</i>	Useful when fever has a parasitic or microbial basis
<i>Ojovardhana</i>	Enhance Immunity

Types of Jwara and useful drugs of Guduchyadivarga,

The following drugs mentioned in Guduchyadivarga, are effective against various Jwara were enumerated here

Table 4: Types of *Jwara* and useful drugs of *Guduchyadi Varga*.

Drugs as per Guduchyadi Varga	Dosha Specific Jwara
Trivrit	Vata jwara
<i>Parpataka, Sariva</i>	<i>Pitta, Rakta Jwara</i>
<i>Sindhuvara , Yavasa</i>	<i>Kapha Jwara</i>
<i>Murva , Kakamachi</i>	<i>Tridosha Jwara</i>
<i>Gunja , Mashaparni</i>	<i>Vatapitta Jwara</i>
<i>Vasa , Nimba, Trayamana</i>	<i>Kaphapitta jwara</i>
<i>Agnimantha , Patha, Bilwa</i>	<i>Vatakapha jwara</i>

Table 5: Types of Fevers and useful drugs of *Guduchyadivarga*, (Research studies)

Effective Drugs from Guduchyadi Varga	Fevers
<i>Parpataka</i> . ^[4] <i>Gunja</i> . ^[5]	Viral fevers (Influenza)
<i>Patha</i> . ^[6] <i>Nirgundi</i> . ^[7]	Malaria and intermittent fevers
<i>Sarapunkh</i> . ^[8] <i>Kakamachi</i>	Hepatic fevers or Yakritgata Jwara
<i>Parpataka</i> . ^[8] <i>Nimba, Guduchi</i> . ^[9]	Fever with skin eruptions (German Measles)
<i>Vasa</i> . ^[10] <i>Patha, Datura, Guduchi, Arka</i> . ^[11]	Dengue fever
<i>Kumar</i> . ^[12]	Fever with Neutropenia
<i>Guduchi</i> . ^[13,14] <i>Neem</i> . ^[15,16] <i>Nirgundi</i> , <i>Vasa</i> . ^[17]	Typhoid and enteric fevers
<i>Patha</i> . ^[18,19] <i>Guduchi</i> . ^[20]	Covid -19

Table 6: Compound formulation made from Guduchyadivarga, used in various fevers.

<i>Guduchyadi kashayam21</i>	<i>Sarva Jwara</i>
<i>Shadanga paneeya, Pachana kashaya</i>	<i>Ama Jwara</i>
<i>Saribadi vati, Gopichandanadi vati</i>	<i>Pitta-Rakta Jwara</i>
<i>Mahatiktaka ghrita</i>	<i>Twak Vikara with Jwara</i>

DISCUSSION

The *Guduchyadivarga*, from *Bhavaprakasha Nighantu* contains a wealth of medicinal plants with robust applicability in various types of Jwara. Out of the 190 herbs,^[29] are *Tikta rasa* (bitter) which have *Jwarahara* property targeting both the gastrointestinal system (to eliminate Ama) and the toxins in blood (to clear Rakta Dushti). In the context of jwara, Rakta Dushti can be explained on the basis of core Ayurvedic core ayurvedic principle **Asraya - Ashrayibhava** Sambandha describing the inter dependent relationship between a substratum (ashraya) and the entity that resides in it (ashrayi). It explains how body components dosha, dhatu and mala rely on each other. In Jwara the aggravated pitta (Ashrayi) disturbs rakta (Ashraya), hence treating Pitta will relieve Rakta Dushti. The efficacy of tikta rasa (bitter drugs) can be explained in terms of its **Amapachana** property which helps in relieving Ama. It also helps in relieving excessive pitta, thus reduces jwara and purifies rakta. thirst in fever is also relieved by its *Trishnahara* property. As *Jwara* affects both body & mind (*Dehendriya Manasantapo*) Tikta rasa having **Medhya** property will help in proper blood circulation to brain and aids in relieving stress & calming the mind (*vaichitya nashana*). Tikta rasa is **Dipana, Pachana.**^[22] *swayam arochaka* but helps in curing *Aruchi* caused during *Jwara*. *Guduchi*, a cornerstone of this varga, stands out due to its *Rasayana* and *Jwarahara* properties. supporting anti-inflammatory, hepatoprotective, and antimicrobial actions, aligning closely with classical descriptions. Hence *Guduchyadivarga*, represents grouping of herbs with broad-spectrum antipyretic, immunomodulatory, and anti-inflammatory properties. These drugs were mainly useful in *Ama Jwara*, *Pitta*-dominant fevers, and chronic low-grade fevers with systemic inflammation.

CONCLUSION

A review on *Guduchyadivarga*, from *Bhavaprakasha Nighantu* elucidates a rich legacy of Ayurvedic knowledge concerning the treatment of Jwara and other associated febrile conditions. *Guduchyadivarga*, offers an effective pharmacological grouping in managing febrile illnesses. With its *Tridosahara*, *Jwaraghna*, and *Rasayana* properties, these herbs not only alleviate symptoms but also address the underlying doshic and toxic imbalances. Their modern relevance is also evident in the treatment of viral fevers, enteric diseases, and inflammatory conditions. A judicious combination of these drugs can be integrated into contemporary fever management with classical Ayurvedic rationale and Modern Diagnostics.

REFERENCES

1. <https://niimh.nic.in/ebooks/ecaraka/?mod=read> Charaka Nidana Sthana Chapter 1 Jwara Nidana verse 4 date 13-12-2025
2. SD Kamath, Studies on Medicinal Plants and Drugs in Bhava Prakas Hanighantu, Chaukambha Pratisthan, Varanasi, Edition, 2018; 1. ISBN 978-81-7084-726-7, 351- 658.
3. Dwivedi R.B., Dubey S.D., Gujarathi R., Singh A.Khandel S.K., Rai S.. Jwara Nidana Adhyaya. In: Khandel S.K., Godatwar P., Deole Y.S., Basisht G., eds. Charak Samhita New Edition. 1st ed. Jamnagar, Ind: CSRTSDC; 2020. https://www.carakasamhitaonline.com/index.php?title=Jwara_Nidana&oldid=44497. Accessed August 17, 2025.
4. Archana Sharma *etal.*, From roots to remedies: Exploration of medicinal potential of *Fumaria parviflora* Lam. in drug discovery, Pharmacological Research - Natural Products, 2025; 8: 100319, ISSN 2950 1997, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.prenap.2025.100319>. (<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S295019972500179X>)
5. Sanika Gondkar *etal.*, A Review Article on One Specific Semipoisonous Herb: Gunja, International Journal of Pharmaceutical Research and Applications, July-Aug 2023; 8(4): 2583-2589. www.ijprajournal.com ISSN: 2249-7781
6. Hikal, Wafaa & Alhawiti, Latifah S. Eid & Mahmoud, Abeer & Tkachenko, Kirill & Said-Al Ahl, Hussein. (2021). *Cissampelos pareira*: A potential source of medicine to treat malaria. International Journal of Mosquito Research, 8: 37-43.
7. Dr. Antony Stephen Raj, Dr. Faiz Mohammed, Dr. Govardhan Sahani, Dr. Arun Prakash, Dr. Mydeen Sadik. Ayurvedic approach towards the management of malaria. Int J Mosq, 2023; 10(6): 138-142. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22271/23487941.2023.v10.i6b.729>
8. Sarapunkha *etc* Devprakash, Sumalatha B.V, K.K. Srinivasan, Savitha. *Tephrosia purpurea* (Linn.) Pers.- A Comprehensive Review. Research J. Pharmacognosy and Phytochemistry, 2012; 4(2): 134-143.
9. R. Somashekhar *et al.* (eds.), Proceedings of the International Conference on Advances in Nano-Neuro-Bio-Quantum (ICAN 2023), Advances in Intelligent Systems Research, 69. https://doi.org/10.2991/978-94-6463-294-1_12
10. Patole, Lalita Nivrutti; Hend, Apoorwa Kishor. A Review Article of Chickenpox Management Via Ayurveda. Journal of Preventive, Diagnostic and Treatment Strategies in Medicine, Jul-Sep 2023; 2(3): 135-138. | DOI: 10.4103/jpdtm.jpdtm_90_23
11. Thanigaivel A, Chandrasekaran R, Revathi K, Nisha S, Sathish-Narayanan S, Kirubakaran

- SA, Senthil-Nathan S. Larvicidal efficacy of *Adhatoda vasica* (L.) Nees against the bancroftian filariasis vector *Culex quinquefasciatus* Say and dengue vector *Aedes aegypti* L. in in vitro condition. *Parasitol Res.*, 2012 May; 110(5): 1993-9. doi: 10.1007/s00436-011-2728-2. Epub 2011 Dec 14. PMID: 22167370.
12. Kamaraj C, Ragavendran C, Prem P, Naveen Kumar S, Ali A, Kazmi A, Ullah A, Chandra Satish Kumar R, Khan SU, Luna-Arias JP, Mashwani ZU, Balasubramani G, Rehman SU. Exploring the Therapeutic Potential of Traditional Antimalarial and Antidengue Plants: A Mechanistic Perspective. *Can J Infect Dis Med Microbiol.* 2023 Oct 28; 2023: 1860084. doi: 10.1155/2023/1860084. PMID: 37927532; PMCID: PMC10625492.
13. Schönknecht K, Kulawik AM, Krauss H, Fal AM. Efficacy And Safety Of Candelabra Aloe Extract (*Aloe Arborescens* Mill.) In Prevention And Treatment Of Upper Respiratory Tract Infections Of Various Aetiologies. *Wiad Lek.*, 2022; 75(12): 3123-3127. doi: 10.36740/WLek202212138. PMID: 36723337.
14. Hussain L, Akash MS, Ain NU, Rehman K, Ibrahim M. The Analgesic, Anti-Inflammatory and Anti-Pyretic Activities of *Tinospora cordifolia*. *Adv Clin Exp Med.*, 2015 Nov-Dec; 24(6): 957-64. doi: 10.17219/acem/27909. PMID: 26771966.
15. Sahare Priyanka et al: Conceptual Study of Guduchi In The Management Of Jwara. *International Ayurvedic Medical Journal* {online} 2020 {cited November, 2020} Available from: http://www.iamj.in/posts/images/upload/2612_2616.pdf
16. X M. Oyedeji-Amusa, N. Cuboia, K. Olofinisan, Medicinal Plants Used in the Treatment of Typhoid Fever in Nigeria: A Systematic Review, *Journal of Herbal Medicine*, 2024; 47: 100930, ISSN 2210-8033, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.hermed.2024.100930>. (<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2210803324000873>)
17. Muhammad Ali, Muhammad S. Abdallah, Rabiou M. Kutama, Antityphoid Activity and Phytochemical Screening of *Azadirachta Indica* Leaf Extracts, *Sci J Research & Rev*, 2020; 2(4):. SJRR,MS.ID.000541
18. Kumar, Manoj and Dandapat, Sukumar and Kumar, Amit and Sinha, M. P., Anti-typhoid Activity of *Adhatoda Vasica* and *Vitex Negundo*, September 2013; 2(3): 64-75. *Persian Gulf Crop Protection*, Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3952769>
19. Haider M, Anand V, Enayathullah MG, Parekh Y, Ram S, Kumari S, Anmol, Panda G, Shukla M, Dholakia D, Ray A, Bhattacharyya S, Sharma U, Bokara KK, Prasher B, Mukerji M. Anti-SARS-CoV-2 potential of *Cissampelos pareira* L. identified by connectivity map-based analysis and in vitro studies. *BMC Complement Med Ther.* 2022 Apr 22; 22(1): 114. doi: 10.1186/s12906-022-03584-3. PMID: 35459166; PMCID:

PMC9028906.

20. Panda AK, Kar S, Rai AK, Rao BCS, Srikanth N. AYUSH- 64: A potential therapeutic agent in COVID-19. *J Ayurveda Integr Med.* 2022 Apr-Jun; 13(2): 100538. doi: 10.1016/j.jaim.2021.100538. Epub 2022 Jan 4. PMID: 35002178; PMCID: PMC8723836.
21. Sadhana Misar Wajpeyi and Ashish U. Nimbhorkar, Role Of Guduchi (*Tinospora Cordifolia*) In Covid-19– A Review. *Int. J. Life Sci. Pharma Res.*, 2023; 13(3): L78-L87. <http://dx.doi.org/10.22376/ijlpr.2023.13.3.SP1.L78-L87>
22. Pal, S., Aku, R., Rath, S., Khandelwal, R., & Mahajon, B. (2017). THERAPUTIC CONTEMPLATION OF ANCIENT AYURVEDA ON GUDUCHI-
23. TINOSPORA CORDIFOLIA (WILLD.) MIERS. *International Journal of Current Research.*
24. Ganga Sahay Pandey (editor) *Caraka Samhita Sutrasthana Chapter 26, Verse 43*, Varanasi, Chaukambha Sanskrit Sansthan, 2001; 506.